

Role of NSS Volunteers in Disaster Management : A Case Study of Five Quake-Affected Villages of Marathwada

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Abstract : *Youth Power is the answer to the world's biggest problems. The NSS programme launched in India to instilling the idea of social welfare in students.*

In Killari, a place in Marathwada region in Maharashtra, where a colossal quake struck in 1993, claiming about 10,000 lives and destroying properties in fifty-two villages around Latur and Osmanabad districts. The NSS volunteers did an exemplary job in these areas. The present research works proposes to evaluate the role and the emergent impact of NSS volunteerism in complementing relief operations during this quake.

The present study seeks to test hypotheses like potential of youth power is very important in disaster management. This research work used primary and secondary data to analyse the role of NSS in disaster management.

Primary data has been obtained using sampling survey technique through structured questionnaire administered to respondents spread across the five most affected villages of two districts.

Keywords : NSS, Disaster Management, Shramadan, Volunteerism.

National Service Scheme (NSS) : A Symbol of Youth Potential and Volunteerism

India has the largest youth population in the world which constitutes a vibrant and dynamic segment of the country's population and is potentially the most valuable human resource. In view of the large strength and country-wide presence of the youth volunteers of the NSS scheme and to tap the constructive and creative energies of the youth, interaction was initiated with the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports, Govt. of India that is pursuing the twin objectives of developing the personality of youth and involving them in various nation building activities.

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National Service Scheme was launched in the Mahatma Gandhi Birth Centenary year in 1969, as student youth service Programme. It aims at arousing social consciousness of the youth with an overall objective of personality development of the students through the instrument of community service. The scheme covers all the states and union territories, 174 universities, 7500 colleges and institutions of higher learning. One NSS unit consists of 100 student volunteers led by a teacher in-charge designated as “NSS Programme Officer”.

Importance of sensitization and awareness among the communities to their vulnerabilities and the need to manage them has been felt at the highest levels in Government. With the help of volunteers to sensitize and reach out to communities in rural as well as urban areas, the Ministry aims to make Disaster Management a part of the everyday life of a common man.

Over the years, the NSS Programs have been influencing the young minds to extend a helping hand towards addressing social problems in the country, and have been motivating them to tackle development issues in India. The Ministry of Youth Affairs has been spearheading these movements that have had many successes in various spheres of development including response to natural disasters, especially in the recent major disasters, Killari (Latur) earthquake.

NSS volunteers have traditionally been at the forefront of assisting the civil administration in times of national crisis – be it natural disaster or civil strife. The organization has been active in relief management and distribution. These trained volunteers are also facilitating the process of building disaster-resilient communities by focusing on disaster mitigation preparedness and response related Programs.

In the area of Disaster Management the primary activities of these organizations is to focus upon, in accordance with their presence and strength on facilitating community-based disaster preparedness planning process as part of their community work, generating awareness among the common people about the mitigation and preparedness measures, undertaking college level disaster awareness and safety Programs especially in the case of NSS since they involve young student volunteers and developing the capacity of the youth in their capacity in first aid and search and rescue so as to enable them to assist the civil administration in times of emergencies.

The Programme envisages an important role for the youth volunteers in facilitating community plans to cope with disasters, identifying members of taskforces and training them in different aspects of disaster management. These

youth volunteers are trained in facilitating development of community-based disaster management plans, awareness activities and in implementation of college awareness and safety plans. Amongst the success stories under this programme are several initiatives in the state of Maharashtra. (GOI-UNDP: 2009)

Killari (Latur) Earthquake

A strong earthquake of magnitude 6.4 on the Richter scale struck the Marathwada region of south central Maharashtra on September 30, 1993. (GSI, 1996; Gupta, 1996; Jain, 1994) This natural disaster resulted in extensive damage to life and property leaving 10,000 persons and 15,854 livestock dead, and 16,000 people injured. Fifty-two villages were demolished in the intra-plate earthquake (wikipedia.org), 30,000 houses collapsed, almost two lakh houses in 13 districts suffered damages of varying degree, nearly 127000 families were affected by this colossal quake.(latur.nic.in)

The life in the affected villages was paralysed. Donor agencies and social organisations carried out extensive rescue and relief operations. The Government, social organisations and NGOs contributed their best to bring the life to normal. (Physicians and staff from Railway Hospital, Solapur and V.M. Medical College, Solapur were amongst the first to reach the site and assisted with treatment of the injured over the next several weeks.) The government has formulated detailed rehabilitation policy within six months of the incidence and a huge programme of rehabilitation of damaged villages was taken up with the help of World Bank and other donor agencies. This rescue and rehabilitation work has been completed with the help of social and non- governmental organizations, in which the volunteers of National Service Scheme (NSS) of various colleges have played a pivotal role. This is a unique example of the use of youth potential in disaster management.

Disaster Management

The United Nations defines a disaster as a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society. Disasters involve widespread human, material, economic or environmental impacts, which exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope using its own resources.

While no country is immune from disaster, its vulnerability to disaster varies. There are four main types of disaster i.e. Natural disasters, Environmental emergencies, Complex emergencies and Pandemic emergencies. The earthquake is categorized as a Natural disaster.

Any disaster can interrupt essential services, such as health care, electricity, water, sewage/garbage removal, transportation and communications. The interruption can seriously affect the health, social and economic networks of local communities and countries. Disasters have a major and long-lasting impact on people long after the immediate effect has been mitigated. Poorly planned relief activities can have a significant negative impact not only on the disaster victims but also on donors and relief agencies.

Local, regional, national and international organisations are all involved in mounting a humanitarian response to disasters. Each will have a prepared disaster management plan. These plans cover prevention, preparedness, relief and recovery.

Disaster prevention – These are activities designed to provide permanent protection from disasters. Not all disasters, particularly natural disasters, can be prevented, but the risk of loss of life and injury can be mitigated with good evacuation plans, environmental planning and design standards. In January 2005, 168 Governments adopted a 10-year global plan for natural disaster risk reduction called the Hyogo Framework. It offers guiding principles, priorities for action, and practical means for achieving disaster resilience for vulnerable communities.

Disaster preparedness – These activities are designed to minimise loss of life and damage – for example by removing people and property from a threatened location and by facilitating timely and effective rescue, relief and rehabilitation. Preparedness is the main way of reducing the impact of disasters. Community-based preparedness and management should be a high priority in physical therapy practice management.

The need for the disaster management initiative was recognized in the initial working papers of the World Bank project team (World Bank, 1993) The principal objective here was to engage in disaster management is to reduce vulnerability of the population and the built environment before disasters occur; to minimize life and property loss, enhance populations resilience by providing development opportunities, and to ensure environmental viability for future generations.

Disaster relief – This is a coordinated multi-agency response to reduce the impact of a disaster and its long-term results. Relief activities include rescue, relocation, providing food and water, preventing disease and disability, repairing vital services such as telecommunications and transport, providing temporary shelter and emergency health care.

Disaster recovery – Once emergency needs have been met and the initial crisis is over, the people affected and the communities that support them are still vulnerable. Recovery activities include rebuilding infrastructure, health care and rehabilitation. These should blend with development activities, such as building human resources for health and developing policies and practices to avoid similar situations in future. (www.wcpt.org)

Role of NSS Volunteers in Disaster Management : A Study of Youth Potential in Disaster Management in Killari Earthquake

This paper seeks to study the role of NSS volunteers in post-disaster relief activity after a disastrous earthquake struck the Killari village and its surroundings (Latur district in Maharashtra). The quake occurred in wee hours of 30th September 1993.

Primary data has been collected from the five affected villages, namely Killari, Shirsal, Yalvat, KillariVadi and Talani, which fall under the jurisdiction of AUSA tehsil of Latur district. A total 50 affected respondents from five villages have been interviewed. Each respondent was given twenty structured questions. Data received by way of their responses has been analyzed. Respondents comprised 39 males and 11 females between age group 41 and 86 years.

The residents of this areas lost several family members and friends in this disaster. With their houses flattened, most of them were buried under the rubble. And many of those who survived were badly injured or permanently handicapped. Damage to the properties was huge, but the loss of lives was most excruciating.

A number of organizations came forward to help them, in which Baba Aamte's Anandwan, RSS, Bajarang Dal, students from Uttar Pradesh, SarvanginVikas Sanstha, Latur, and others lent a helping hand to them during the time of this Himalayan crisis. Several companies took initiative for rehabilitation work like Shirke, Ketu, Skyline, Tata, Indian Oil, Hindustan Petroleum, Bharat Petroleum, Cole India, World Vision India, Manjara Sugar Factory and so on. NSS volunteers were also involved in rescue operation. They started coming from the very day the tragedy struck. A big number of volunteers were present and although it is hard to point out the exact number, around 100 to 300 volunteers were involved in assisting the survivors of the deadly quake across the affected villages. They stayed up to one month in the village. There were NSS residential camps were organized by the colleges for about two years in the affected villages and under

these volunteers made efforts to rebuild the damaged property and infrastructure in the area.

The volunteers helped in rescue operations, food and water distribution to the affected populace, providing first aid to the injured, assisting in public transportation, making tents and providing temporary residential arrangement to the affected and also assisting farmers in farming work.

In the NSS residential camps volunteers helped in rebuilding roads, revamping sanitation, assisting in building houses, with a focus on hygienic and other developmental measures.

They also tried to educate villagers about the measures to be taken during the post-quake scenario and these included, among other things, moving out of houses into open spaces or grounds as a first step. The volunteers also advised villagers as to what they should do in case the quake strikes and one cannot go out into open. Thus, the volunteers played an important role in the area as people needed psychological support to cope with post-disaster circumstances. They employed the medium of cultural programs, street plays, one-act plays, camping programs, rallies and so on to get their message across.

NSS volunteers did their job as good as NGO activists. The volunteers conducted door-to-door surveys and prepared a comprehensive list of the affected people, detailing the loss of lives and property. This data was very helpful to the administration. NSS volunteers were however not adequately trained for rescue and relief operation, so the relief work has not been up to the mark and there is a need to train these volunteers better. Notwithstanding that, they were fully committed to the cause they undertook to fight for.

Disaster Management Training for NSS Volunteers

The National Service Scheme (NSS) has been setup with an objective of promoting the motive of social service among the citizens of the nation. Since its inception, the NSS, which become a kind of movement in itself, has undergone changes in its form and design in keeping with the changing needs of the nation. The NSS organization has more than 24 lakh volunteers across the country which has been playing a vital role in the disaster response and relief operations for quite a long time.

There is a need to re-orient the roles and responsibilities of NSS volunteers in the light of changes in disaster management approach of the Government of

India. It has been envisaged that this large contingent of volunteers could prove resourceful if they could be trained to assist communities, schools, colleges and other institutions, from where they come or are being posted, disaster preparedness and mitigation. The following roles have been identified as could be played by the NSS volunteers :

- Awareness generation among communities and educational institutions on disaster preparedness and mitigation.
- Help local communities and educational institutions in preparation of disaster management plans.
- Take active role in training the village level disaster management teams in disaster preparedness (for this, skilled volunteers have to be identified).
- Help local administration during disasters in rescue, evacuation, and relief operations.

These volunteer force needs to be trained in various aspects of disaster management to make sure that they perform these new roles in a professional manner.

The following training modules given below could prove helpful to the trainers and training institutions of NSS in conducting such a training programme. The aim of this training is to improve the performance of volunteers in disaster risk management that also helps them in improving their performance during disasters.

Knowledge & Skill Areas – Some focal areas are highlighted for skill development of the volunteers such as, Hazards and their impacts, Disaster management : Principles and Practices, Risk and vulnerability assessment, Preparing disaster management plans (community and school), First aid, Rescue operations, DM planning (School and community), Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA), Developing IEC materials, Reporting skills, Basic survival skills, Strategies for mass awareness generation, Crowd control, Disaster management in India, Counselling, Team-building skills, Relief Distribution, Public Relations, Panic and Rumour Management, Coordination and emergency communication, Personal management, Supervision skills, Disaster management legislation and so on.

There are a total of 24 lakh NSS volunteers in India who need to be trained in various aspects of disaster management.

Implementation Modalities – Looking at the large number of volunteers needs to be trained in various aspects of disaster management, this training design proposes to be implemented in two parts i.e. in Distance Education mode and in Contact Program mode.

a) Distance Education module -

1. The Distance Education module which would be available online provides knowledge on various aspects of disaster management with useful exercises/ assignments for the students. The details of Distance Education module are provided in the Learning Units section.
2. The Distance Education module could be hosted on the NIDM website or NSS website with a two focal points representing NIDM and NSS as course organizers.
3. Regional modules could be designed based on need.
4. To facilitate the distance learning process, the institution level NSS key functionary could act as local level anchor conducting interaction sessions in the school/college as per the online learning schedule every weekend

b) Contact Program -

The Contact Program of the training module would be used to impart disaster management skills where instructors from various specializations would train volunteers on rescue and evacuation, relief distribution, first aid, basic survival skills etc. Refer to the Learning units section for more details

Benefits - Some benefits observed after this training are:

1. Enhanced knowledge and skills in disaster management
2. Increased confidence among volunteers
3. Better communication skills
4. Enhanced social perceptions about NSS
5. Conservation of resources due to better performance (sdmtripura.nic.in)

This type of training is necessary for rural based NSS volunteers for doing their disaster management job with full of skills and perfection.

Conclusion

The role played by the NSS volunteers in disaster management in the above noted villages reflect the channeling of youth power to a social cause. Although these youngsters were not professionally trained in the disaster management, they did an excellent job of helping in relief and rescue operations. Beginning with the activity like 'shramadan', the NSS volunteers made commendable efforts to alleviate the suffering of the distraught villagers. It is important to note that in a deadly quake like one mentioned above, administration alone cannot come up to the colossal task. NSS volunteers complimented the efforts of administration by way of food and water distribution, providing first aid and lending a psychological support to the survivors of the quake. They even assisted the farmers in tilling the land and harvesting the crops.

However, lack of technical know-how in the area of disaster management threw a spanner in the work of these volunteers. They could have done a better job if they had been adequately trained for the purpose.

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